

GERMPLASM IMPROVEMENT

Genetic resources

Analysis of the pedigrees of japonica rice varieties released in Taiwan

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We studied changes in the genetic diversity of japonica rice varieties released in Taiwan over five time periods: 1940-49, 1950-59, 1960-69, 1970-79, and 1980-89. Relative genetic contributions were computed to quantify the genetic constituents of 99 varieties into theoretical percentages attributable to different ancestors.

The varieties were traced back to 65 ancestors, 44 of them Japanese plant introductions. Only 11 were from Taiwan. Japanese introductions contributed more than 85% of the genes. Although more ancestors were integrated into later breeding programs, as few as

Relative genetic contributions and occurrence of the 10 most important ancestral contributors to 99 varieties released in Taiwan 1940-89.

Ancestor	Mean genetic contribution	Cumulative genetic contribution	Occurrence (no.) in pedigrees
Hodoyoshi	0.213	0.213	83
Kameji	0.167	0.380	80
NC 4	0.065	0.445	45
Oloan-chu	0.061	0.506	43
Iyosengoku	0.037	0.543	26
Aikoku	0.037	0.580	46
Osaka Asahi	0.023	0.603	19
Iwata Asahi	0.020	0.623	23
Kairio Aikoku	0.019	0.642	20
Yoshino I	0.018	0.660	9

10 contributors comprised more than 70% of the genetic constituents of the released varieties in each time period.

Two Japanese introductions predominated in mean relative genetic contributions of genes: Hodoyoshi with 21.3% and Kameji with 16.7% (see table). At least 83 of the 99 varieties released in the last 50 yr (including all 11 varieties released in 1980-87) are more or less related because of the Hodoyoshi link.

This shows the narrow genetic base in current japonica rice varieties. Extensive use of superior varieties such as Taichung 65 is the major reason integration of diverse plant introductions did not result in diversification of released germplasm. Crosses to elite genotypes that carry specific gene complexes conditioning desirable traits should be made with caution, to avoid decreasing the genetic diversity among released varieties. ■

Widely compatible japonica rice from Yunnan, China

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Yunnan local rice variety Haomei carries resistance to nine strains of bacterial blight (*Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzae*): Jiangling 691, OS75, 76-27, and KS-6-6 from China and PXO61, PXO86, PXO79, PXO71, and PXO211 from the Philippines. It is susceptible to strain PXO99 from the Philippines.

Resistance of Haomei to Chinese strain Jiangling 691 is governed by a newly identified dominant gene, tentatively designated as *Xa-i*. *Xa-i* is linked to the marker gene *nl-1* (neck leaf-1) located on linkage group 5. The recom-

bination value between *Xa-i* and *nl-1* is $37.3 \pm 3.9\%$ by maximum likelihood estimation.

Haomei is a widely compatible japonica. Fertility with indica testers is $73.72 \pm 4.63\%$; that with japonica testers is $77.13 \pm 11.08\%$.

Haomei has glabrous leaf and hull and glutinous endosperm. The hull is covered

with purple blots, with fewer over the glume bulge. Rice base-solubility (1.7% KOH treatment for 23 h under 30 °C) belongs to grade 4.

It is medium-tillering with large panicles averaging 239 grains. Grain weight is 35.2 g per 1000. Plant height is about 120 cm in Wuchang, Hubei Province. ■

Genetics

Heritability of seedling vigor characters

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Poor seedling emergence associated with seedling vigor characters is a major constraint to the adoption of direct seeding for irrigated and rainfed lowland rice. Heritability is the fraction of variation in a trait that is attributable to

genetic causes. It is a property not only of a character, but also of the plant population and the environmental circumstances of the crop.

We used variance partitioning of segregating populations (VPSP) and offspring:parent ($F_3:F_2$) regression and correlation in four crosses to estimate narrow sense heritability (H_n) for mesocotyl, coleoptile, and seedling length.

H_n for mesocotyl length was comparatively higher than for coleoptile and seedling length (see table). The

offspring:parent regression was the least variable of the estimates among populations (indicated by the low CV). Among the characters, mesocotyl length estimates were least variable.

This means early generation selection for seedling emergence should be more effective using mesocotyl length. Early generation selection using coleoptile and seedling length can be done only in selected crosses. Otherwise, selection would be more effective in later generations, accompanied by progeny testing. ■

Narrow sense heritability (Hn) estimates for mesocotyl, coleoptile, and seedling length in rice, measured by variance partitioning (VPSP) and offspring:parent F₃:F₂ regression (regr) and correlation (corr).

Cross	Hn estimates											
	Mesocotyl				Coleoptile				Seedling			
	VPSP	Regr	Corr	Mean	VPSP	Regr	Corr	Mean	VPSP	Regr	Corr	Mean
ITA212/Nato	53.7	64.7	49.0	55.8	30.4	40.7	54.2	41.8	48.3	26.7	35.0	36.7
TN1/Nato	30.6	71.4	63.3	55.1	67.6	35.6	48.7	50.6	30.3	27.4	33.2	30.3
TN1/ITA323	61.8	71.4	84.1	72.4	61.6	37.8	46.1	48.5	50.3	33.2	20.0	34.5
IR64/ITA212	50.0	52.7	63.1	61.1	21.2	18.7	26.2	22.0	35.2	26.5	40.3	34.0
Mean	49.0	65.1	64.9	59.7	45.2	33.2	43.8	40.7	41.0	28.5	32.1	33.9
CV	26.9	13.5	22.3	11.9	50.5	29.8	27.9	38.1	23.9	11.2	26.9	26.3

Genetic and cytoplasmic sources of IR varieties 1967-84

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Genetic diversity of cytoplasm sources for released varieties is important because genetic uniformity could lead to devastating disease epidemics. We used a computer program written in PASCAL to examine the pedigrees of 27 *Oryza sativa* L. IR lines released 1967-84.

The pedigrees show that the 27 varieties can be traced back to 26 ancestors,

of which 5 appear only once. Ten ancestors comprise 75% of the relative genetic contribution. Three dominate in mean relative genetic contribution: Dee-geo-woo-gen, 16%; Cina, 12.6%; and Latisail, 12.6%. Dee-geo-woo-gen appears in the pedigree of 26 of the 27 varieties; Cina and Latisail are in the pedigrees of all varieties. This makes the 27 varieties examined more or less related. More ancestors have been integrated into recent varieties.

Four cultivars were ultimate maternal ancestors, and thus contributed cytoplasm to all 27 varieties (see table). Cina contributed its cytoplasm to 22 of the 27 varieties, and is the most

Cytoplasm parents for 27 varieties released at IRRI.

Cytoplasm parent	IR lines				
Nam Sagui 19 Cina	IR52	IR54			
	IR5	IR28	IR38	IR50	
	IR8	IR29	IR40	IR56	
	IR20	IR30	IR42	IR58	
	IR22	IR32	IR45	IR60	
	IR24	IR34	IR46		
Marong-Paroc Arikarai	IR26	IR36	IR48		
	IR43	IR44			
	IR62				

important contributor of both nuclear and cytoplasmic genes to the IR varieties. ■

Effect of germinating condition and plant growth regulator on rate of twin seedlings from polyembryonic rice

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Polyembryonic rice—characterized by twin seedlings—is a good genetical tool for apomixis research. We studied four selected heritable polyembryonic rices.

Adventitious embryos had low frequencies (2.6-5.1%). The apparent primary mode of polyembryonic rice is twin seedlings, but there is an internal relationship between the rate of twin seedlings and the rate of adventitious embryos.

We experimented with the effect of germinating condition on twin seedling rate in Shuang 3 (indica), Shuang 13

Table 1. Rates of twin seedlings under different germinating conditions.

Variety	Rate (%) of twin seedlings							
	Germinated in distilled water (25°C)	Germinated in N6 (25°C) (with no pretreatment)	Germinated in N6 media (25 °C) with wet pretreatment ^a (5 h)					
			0°C	10°C	20°C	30°C	40°C	50°C
Shuang 3 (indica)	41.0	48.4	17.1	65.8	67.5	75.0	70.5	42.5
Shuang 13 (indica)	5.3	7.7	5.3	12.9	7.4	13.2	6.9	16.6
Lu 52 (japonica)	6.5	13.2	6.7	11.1	7.9	13.1	8.8	24.5
Alixisini (japonica)	2.0	3.1	0	1.9	3.9	1.9	1.6	4.4

^a There was no germination at 60°C.

(indica), Lu 52 (japonica), and Alixisini (japonica). Germinating seeds without hulls resulted in higher rates of twin seedlings than germinating seeds with hulls. The highest increase was 3.8%.

The rate of twin seedlings increased when the germination test was done in

N6 media. The twin seedling rate varied with pregermination treatment at different temperatures (Table 1). The optimum pretreatment temperature was 50°C for two japonicas and one indica and 30°C for the other indica. At optimum temperature, the rate of twin seedlings